

Comparative Study of IaC Frameworks (Terraform, Ansible, OpenTofu, Pulumi) for Multi-Cloud Deployment Performance and Security

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Abstract—The adoption of hybrid and multi-cloud strategies has made Infrastructure as Code (IaC) critical for achieving automated, scalable, and repeatable deployment environments, mainly within Continuous Integration / Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) pipelines. Integrating IaC tools on the CI/CD pipelines, infrastructure provisioning, configuration and updates occur in a consistent and repeatable way. This research provides a theoretical comparative analysis of Terraform, Ansible, OpenTofu and Pulumi as IaC tools within the deployment environment.

Index Terms—Infrastructure as Code, Terraform, Ansible, OpenTofu, Pulumi, Multi-Cloud, Performance, Security

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid expansion of cloud computing has transformed how organisations design, deploy, and manage Information Technology (IT) infrastructure. As enterprises increasingly adopt hybrid and multi-cloud strategies to leverage the strengths of different cloud providers, the need for automation, scalability, and repeatability in infrastructure provisioning has become critical. IaC has emerged as a key enabler of this paradigm, allowing infrastructure resources to be defined, version-controlled, and provisioned through machine-readable configuration files rather than manual processes. IaC frameworks such as Terraform, Ansible, OpenTofu, and Pulumi have gained prominence for their ability to automate cloud provisioning, streamline DevOps workflows, and enhance deployment reliability. Despite their shared objective, these tools differ significantly in their architecture, operational models, state management approaches, and security mechanisms. To optimise cloud performance, it is essential to perform a comprehensive analysis of each IaC framework over another, while also ensuring security compliance and reducing operational complexity. This research provides a theoretical comparison of each IaC framework, focusing on the multi-cloud deployment performance and security. Analysing academic literature, official documentation and architecture principles, it was possible to evaluate key aspects such as configuration models, state management, dependency handling, scalability, secrets management and policy enforcement.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

IaC has evolved as a response to the complexity and scale of modern cloud environments, automating infrastructure provisioning. Instead of relying on shell scripts and manual configuration steps, which lacked standardisation, reproducibility

and consistency, IaC emerged as a response to the growing complexity and scale of modern cloud environments.

The effective implementation of IaC relies on several key principles that ensure scalability, consistency, and reliability throughout the infrastructure lifecycle [1]. These principles define best practices for structuring, managing, and automating infrastructure code to ensure predictable and maintainable deployments, as outlined below.

- **Version Control** - Infrastructure definitions and configuration should be stored in a Version Control System (e.g, Git) to track changes and ensure that the entire infrastructure setup is reproducible, auditable and consistent across environments.
- **Modularity and Reuse** - IaC promotes breaking the infrastructure into small modules and components, increasing the maintainability and reusability across environments.
- **Idempotence** - Ensure that executing the same infrastructure definitions repeatedly results in the same infrastructure state, preserving the desired configuration and preventing unintended changes.
- **Automation** - Automate the provisioning, testing, validation, and deployment of infrastructure through pipelines, ensuring that all changes are verified before reaching production. This automation minimises human error and accelerates feedback cycles.

Declarative and imperative paradigms are central concepts on IaC as defined by how infrastructure intent is expressed and executed. The declarative approach specifies the desired end state of infrastructure, while imperative models specify the steps to achieve the desired state.

In IaC, security is a critical concern due to misconfigurations can introduce vulnerabilities, exposing sensitive data and allowing unauthorised access. In opposite to traditional approaches IaC automates infrastructure provisioning, which can amplify the risk of insecure configurations at scale. Key practices to enhance IaC security include [2]:

- **Access Policy** - Restrict public access to critical resources and use restrictive policies and permission groups.
- **IP Address Binding** - Limit network traffic to only what is necessary, reducing the attack surface.
- **Least Privilege** - Apply the principle of least privilege

to user roles and permissions, avoiding unnecessary administrative access.

- **Secrets Management** - Store credentials and sensitive information securely, avoiding hard-coded secrets in public repositories.
- **Encryption at Rest** - Ensure the confidentiality and integrity of data stored in cloud resources.
- **Encryption in Transit** - Use secure protocols, such as TLS, for all communications.
- **Logging and Monitoring** - Observe and record activity to enable threat detection and incident response.
- **Software Updates** - Keep infrastructure and services up to date, applying the latest versions and patches to prevent vulnerabilities.

Terraform, Ansible, OpenTofu, and Pulumi offer distinct approaches to infrastructure automation, from declarative and hybrid provisioning to code-driven orchestration. Comparing these tools highlights how their design choices impact efficiency, security, and suitability for multi-cloud environments.

III. INFRASTRUCTURE AS CODE (IAC) TOOLS

1) *Terraform*: Terraform [3], developed by HashiCorp, is a declarative tool for managing infrastructure in complex scenarios, such as multi-cloud environments across different cloud providers (e.g AWS, Azure, Google Cloud, and Kubernetes). It ensures idempotency, meaning infrastructure configurations can be applied repeatedly with consistent results that align with the desired state. When integrated into CI/CD, Terraform can automate both the provisioning and destruction of infrastructure resources, which is essential for developing and testing in isolated environments.

2) *Ansible*: Ansible [4], developed by Red Hat, is a declarative automation tool for managing and orchestrating existing infrastructure. It ensures that systems, applications, and services reach a defined desired state, as specified in playbooks, which are executed on remote systems via SSH. Playbooks allow the definition of tasks such as package management or user administration. Ansible is can be idempotent if playbooks without manual commands are defined, meaning repeated executions do not produce unintended changes. To simplify management, inventories of managed hosts can be defined. This tool is handy for automating infrastructure tasks and ensuring consistent, repeatable scenarios.

3) *OpenTofu*: OpenTofu [5] is a community-driven, open-source fork of Terraform under the Linux Foundation, created to preserve an open ecosystem for declarative IaC. It inherits Terraform's architecture, HCL language, and state-driven model, offering compatibility while evolving independently with open governance and an open provider registry. OpenTofu emphasizes secure state handling, supports encrypted backends and external secret stores, and integrates with policy-as-code frameworks such as OPA. It is increasingly adopted by organizations seeking transparency and flexibility in multi-cloud automation without commercial platform constraints.

4) *Pulumi*: Pulumi [6] is an IaC framework that enables developers to define cloud infrastructure using general-purpose programming languages like Python, TypeScript, Go, and C#. It offers an imperative-hybrid model, allowing developers to describe their desired cloud state by leveraging familiar software engineering principles, such as modularity, testing, and debugging, directly within their infrastructure code. This approach enhances developer productivity and the ability to integrate application and infrastructure definitions. Pulumi is a multi-cloud solution, provisioning resources across major providers like AWS, Azure, and Google Cloud, by converting the code into a deployment plan that interacts with the respective cloud APIs.

IV. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF IAC TOOLS

A. Performance Considerations

Performance in IaC frameworks is influenced by provisioning latency, concurrency, state-management overhead, resource graphs' scaling, and developer iteration speed. In multi-cloud environments, where several providers' APIs, network delays, and complex interdependencies of resources come together, these performance factors turn out to be very crucial.

Amongst these, Terraform is one of the mature tools that excel when provisioning fresh infrastructure on several clouds; its stable ecosystem, remote state management, and module support maintain its performance on large-scale deployments [7], [8].

Conversely, Pulumi may not always be the fastest in raw provisioning latency; it offers superior developer iteration and rapid change-turnaround by using general-purpose languages and richer abstractions [9], [10].

On the other hand, Ansible remains highly effective for the configuration management and orchestration of existing resources but tends to lag when used purely for large-scale multi-cloud provisioning due to its SSH/agentless execution model [11], [12].

Meanwhile, OpenTofu shares much of Terraform's architecture, generally inheriting Terraform's performance profile for making it almost equivalent in large-scale multi-cloud scenarios but not significantly outperforming it.

In deployments that span thousands of resources across several providers and regions, the advantage of Terraform-or equivalently OpenTofu-becomes apparent: its state backend efficiency, module reutilization, and broad provider support help to mitigate latency and drift. On the other hand, in a world where the velocity of change, frequent updates, and close integration of infrastructure and application code are paramount, Pulumi provides faster iteration cycles and developer-centric workflows. Ansible, while of enormous value in change-oriented or post-provisioning operations, is less suitable for initial large-scale cloud resource provisioning.

B. Security Considerations

Security in IaC frameworks depends on secure state management, strong secret handling, policy-as-code enforcement, and the ability to detect misconfiguration or "security smells"

[13]. All these factors are further amplified in multi-cloud deployments, which introduce a complex attack surface and diverse requirements for compliance [2].

Terraform's security posture [3] is mature but ecosystem-dependent: its state file is a critical security boundary whose leakage can expose secrets if handled inappropriately, while strong policy enforcement and secret handling normally require integrating external tools like Sentinel or Vault [11].

By contrast, Pulumi [6] follows a "security-in-language" approach; thus, it handles one of the most prominent risks of state management-it encrypts secrets by default [9]. Moreover, through the use of general-purpose languages, Pulumi allows developers to apply familiar software engineering practices such as automated unit and integration testing directly to validate security and compliance [14].

On the other side, Ansible [4] is commonly used for security remediation and configuration management, such as applying baselines on existing resources, and contains its own "Ansible Vault" for secret handling. Its agentless, imperative nature is, however, less optimized for secure-by-default provisioning of immutable infrastructure compared to state-driven declarative tools [11], [12]. Meanwhile, OpenTofu [5], sharing Terraform's architecture, also inherits its fundamental security model and dependencies. Its principal security differentiator lies in governance, offering an open source, community-driven platform integrated with open policy frameworks [10]. For deployment scenarios that have high demands on compliance, the choice is obvious: Terraform and OpenTofu depend on a mature ecosystem for scanning [13] and policy, while in Pulumi, security validation and secret management are integrated directly into the development workflow [14]. In turn, Ansible remains the strongest choice for post-provisioning security configuration and remediation [11].

C. Multi-Cloud Capabilities

In modern cloud-centric enterprise architectures, the ability of an infrastructure-as-code framework to span multiple cloud providers and support portability across heterogeneous environments is a critical differentiator.

Terraform is designed with multi-provider orchestration in mind: it allows one to declare resources for AWS, Azure, Google Cloud, and many others within a single configuration via provider blocks and aliases, thereby delivering a unified workflow for multi-cloud provisioning[3], [15].

In turn, the main differentiators of Pulumi are the broad cloud and SaaS provider support and the portability between languages. Indeed, its registry lists over 100 provider packages and it allows infrastructure descriptions using general-purpose languages, such as Python, TypeScript, Go, which increases portability across clouds and decreases provider lock-in[9], [16].

Meanwhile, configuration management between environments is really effective with Ansible; still, it is less adequate for fresh provisioning or the orchestration of heterogeneous cloud resources with the unified codebase; and its SSH-based, agentless execution model is better targeted at

hybrid/on-premises tasks than at full multi-cloud drift-free deployments[11], [12].

Last but not least, OpenTofu is a community-governed fork of Terraform, and largely inherits Terraform's provider-agnostic architecture; thus it supports multi-cloud strategies in a very similar manner, although its ecosystem and community maturity are still developing compared to Terraform's [10].

When organizations adopt multi-cloud strategies spanning public clouds, private clouds, or hybrid combinations, the choice of IaC tool becomes less about which clouds are supported and more about how portable and unified the workflow can be. Terraform and OpenTofu offer the strongest cross-cloud abstraction for large-scale infrastructure stacks, Pulumi delivers a developer-centric multi-cloud abstraction layer, and Ansible remains a compelling choice when the task is orchestration of existing infrastructure rather than fresh multi-cloud provisioning.

V. DISCUSSION

When comparing Terraform, Pulumi, Ansible, and OpenTofu along the axes of performance, multi-cloud capability, and security a number of cross-cutting themes emerge that have implications not just for tool choice but the organizational and operational strategy needed to extract their value.

1) *Security*: Security is foundational in the use of IaC, rather than a secondary concern. Because these tools automate large-scale change across cloud infrastructure, a misconfiguration or insecure default can propagate widely and rapidly. Tools that incorporate secure state-handling, secrets management, policy-as-code, and drift detection inherently reduce risk. Pulumi, with its "security-in-language" narrative, integrates developer workflows, secrets encryption, and testing more directly. Terraform - and by extension, OpenTofu - benefit from a mature ecosystem for governance, policy, and state-locking, but that may require additional setup and organisational discipline. Ansible excels for remediation and configuration enforcement of existing systems - but its SSH-based, agentless model is less suited to "secure-by-default" provisioning of large heterogeneous clouds.

2) *Performance*: Performance in IaC goes beyond raw apply time. It includes provisioning latency, concurrency, state management overhead, iteration speed, and scalability of resource graphs. For large-scale multi-cloud deployments, Terraform and OpenTofu remain strong: their state backends, module reuse, provider ecosystems, and optimized graphs mean they handle thousands of resources across clouds robustly. Pulumi's strength lies in iteration speed, developer productivity, and integrations - teams which change infrastructure frequently may find it faster to evolve using Pulumi. Ansible remains very effective for tasks it was optimized for - configuration, orchestration, and existing resource management - but tends to lag when used for first-time large multi-cloud provisioning because its model does not optimize for massive parallel resource creation or complex dependency graphs.

3) *Multi-Cloud Capabilities*: The ability to define, deploy and manage infrastructure across multiple cloud providers is increasingly strategic. Terraform’s provider architecture, aliasing, and mature registry enable a single code-base to target AWS, Azure, GCP, and others, while OpenTofu inherits much of that model. Pulumi distinguishes itself with language-native infrastructure in Python, TypeScript, Go, etc., broad provider coverage, and a developer-centric model of portability. Ansible supports heterogeneous environments and allows orchestration across clouds, but it is less aligned for unified provisioning across many providers in one code-base. Therefore, when organisations commit to public + private + hybrid cloud strategies, the choice of IaC tool becomes less about the number of provider integrations and more about how portable and unified the workflow can be, including how infrastructure, application code, security, and governance are brought together.

4) *Synthesis*: When analyzing these three dimensions together—performance, security, multi-cloud capability—the interplay becomes evident: a tool may offer very fast provisioning but weak security posture; or strong multi-cloud portability but slower iteration; or excellent security but poorer performance at scale. Thus the “best” tool is not universally the fastest or most featured, but the one aligned most closely with the organisation’s deployment scale, team expertise, cloud strategy and security/regulatory requirement.

For example:

- A large enterprise deploying across many clouds and regions, with thousands of resources and strict compliance/regulation, may favour Terraform or OpenTofu for their performance, broad provider ecosystem and mature governance.
- A software-centric team building micro-services, rapidly iterating infrastructure as code, integrating infrastructure and application development, may lean toward Pulumi, trading some raw provisioning speed for developer productivity and integrated security workflows.
- A team that manages existing multi-cloud resources and focuses on configuration, remediation, baseline enforcement rather than fresh provisioning may find Ansible especially effective.

The eventual choice of IaC framework should, therefore, be based not only on their features but also the organisational context: maturity of DevOps/DevSecOps practices, skills in general-purpose languages or operators, governance and compliance maturity, speed and scale demands, multi-cloud complexity and risk tolerance. Tool choice thus becomes a strategic alignment decision, not just a technical comparison.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper examined four key Infrastructure as Code frameworks—namely, Terraform, Pulumi, Ansible, and OpenTofu—focused on three critical dimensions: performance, multi-cloud capabilities, and security.

We found that Terraform and OpenTofu are particularly well-suited for large, multi-cloud deployments due to mature

state management, broad provider support, and modular architectures. Pulumi, on the other hand, excels with strong developer productivity and rapid iteration, especially suited for teams that treat infrastructure as code by using general-purpose languages. Ansible remains a suitable choice for the configuration management and orchestration of existing infrastructure; however, it is less ideal for large-scale, multi-cloud first-time provisions.

Pulumi’s built-in encryption and developer-centric workflows streamline secrets and policy-as-code integration from a security point of view. Terraform and OpenTofu provide great ecosystems for governance and state-locking but require disciplined tooling and processes. Ansible fits best for post-provisioning enforcement, while it is less aligned for provisioning-first security workflows.

Ultimately, there’s no one-size-fits-all IaC solution. The best solution depends on the organisational context of team skills, deployment scale, cloud strategy, security and regulatory requirements, and iteration frequency. Matching tool capabilities with such factors will better align the organisations to realize their promise of automated, scalable, secure infrastructure provisioning across heterogeneous cloud environments.

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